

The Relationship Between Ostracism and Turnover Intention: Role of Commitment as a Mediator

Nazim Ali* Zahid Ali† Adnan Khan‡

Abstract

The basic objective of this study is to examine the mediating role of OC between WO and TI among the teaching faculty of universities of KP, Pakistan. Data were collected via questionnaires from 207 teachers. SPSS and Amos were used to analyze the data. The results revealed a significant positive relationship between WO and turnover intention, while a significant negative relationship between WO and OC and between OC and TI was confirmed. The results also revealed a significant partial mediation of OC between WO and turnover intention.

Key Words:

Workplace
Ostracism,
Turnover
Intention,
Teachers;
Organizational
Commitment

Introduction

Employees' turnover problems are faced by almost all organizations of the world irrespective of their location and business type (Long, Thean, et al. 2012). Contemporary organizations make strong efforts for searching qualified employees and striving for retention of the available staff (García-Chas, Neira-Fontela, et al. 2014). They are giving more attention to effective human resources because it is an essential component among organizational components for its smooth running.

Employees' turnover has long term negative effects such as decreased efficiency and an increase in unnecessary costs (Allen & Griffeth 2001). It also disturbs operational stability and endangers organizational goals' attainment (Hom & Kinicki 2001). Hollman, Abbasi, et al. (2008) suggest that organizations are cost by turnover in terms of employee quit, searching for new employees, and expenses incur on new employee(s) selection process. Additionally, it deteriorates

* Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies, University of Malakand, KP, Pakistan.
Email: nazimali100@yahoo.com

† Lecturer, Department of Management Studies, University of Malakand, KP, Pakistan.

‡ Lecturer, Department of Management Studies, University of Malakand, KP, Pakistan.

the organization's reputation, decreases customers' loyalty towards the organization, and increases the workload on the employees.

Employees' turnover affects the organization through direct as well as indirect costs. Direct costs refer to the expenses made on advertisement, recruitment, selection, training, etc. of new employees. Indirect costs refer to workload, low productivity, overtime expenses, and spoiled morale of the workers (Martin, 2011). Additionally, non-monetary costs such as an organization's tarnished image, customers' decreased loyalty, and these would be connected with a lasting negative impact on the organization (Long, Thean, et al. 2012). Therefore, it is indispensable for the organizations to manage employees' TI effectively, to cope with the problems associated with employees' turnover.

WO is shunning as a kind of relational abuse investigated to welcome adverse consequences on workforce' perspectives toward work, for example, increased TI, decreased individual prosperity, such as psychological distress and emotional exhaustion (Ferris, Brown, et al. 2008, Wu, Yim et al. 2012). Given the negative attitudinal effect, working ostracism exclusion can be adverse to organizational effectiveness, as ostracized employees may lessen their commitment to citizenship behavior that can individually and collectively benefit the organization (Ferris, Lian, et al. 2015). Variables in the studies have a relationship between WO and TI with a mediating role of OC.

A study examined workforce exclusion. The results indicated that in the last 6 months, 13% of the workers eliminated (Hitlan, Kelly, et al. 2006). Similarly, another study in the United States endured to find out the association between racism and workplace bullying. It was found that over five years' period, 66% of the workforce complained about poor treatment. Out of that 29 % communicated that others left the room upon their entry and 18% were moved to isolation at their workplace (Fox and Stallworth 2005). Attention and recognition are sought by humans since inception. However, being ignored and isolated is experienced by many in society and the workplace. Ostracism reported being an important facet of human life in the ancient recorded history. For example, Greek would vote to isolate individuals from their community as punishment. Even if the degree of ostracism is nominal still it would have a significant association with a sense of belongingness. Ostracism resembles social death (Sommer, Williams, et al. 2001). It portrays the scenario of the world after one's death, thus, adversely affecting human's sense of meaningful existence (Pyszczynski, Greenberg, et al. 2004). Similarly, a study based on the data collected from 304 supervisors and subordinated of different hotels operating in china; aimed to investigate the impact of ostracism on employees' performance and workplace engagement. The model of the study was based on the Conservation of Resources Theory with the longitudinal model. It was found that WO had a negative relationship with work engagement and service quality of the workers (Leung, Wu et al. 2011). Conservation of resources theory suggests that people endeavor for protection and preservation of

the valuable things, termed as resources. The research revealed an optimal combination of personal and job resources improved employees' effectiveness (Wright and Hobfoll 2004).

Organizational commitment is the harmony between an employee and organizational goals where the employee realizes organizational goals as personal and exerts efforts in achieving them (Alimohammadi & Neyshabor, 2013). It refers to an employee's willingness and desire to contribute to an organization's success (Supriyanto, 2013). The reasons behind this commitment could be emotional attachment, moral attachment, and willingness to keep employment in the organization (Balassiano & Salles, 2012; Dey, 2012; Ellenbecker & Cushman, 2012). Organizational commitment has three types which are normative, affective, and continuance commitment (Mouhamadou, 2015). In normative commitment, employee realizes to stay with the organization as a moral obligation (Balassiano & Salles, 2012).

Replete literature identified organizational commitment role in retaining employees. High committed employees are more likely to stay with the working organization (Larkin, 2015). In words of (Aamodt, 2007), employees who have more commitment towards the firm like to stay in the firm, like work attainment, perform well, and show positive behaviors. Employees having a high degree of organizational commitment demonstrate satisfaction with the organization (Azeem & Akhtar, 2014) and satisfaction with the organization decreases the intention to live the organization. Organizational commitment works like handcuffs in resisting employee's departure from the corporation (Siders, George, & Dharwadkar, 2001). Wan (2012) suggests that an employee with a high degree of organizational commitment not only tries to be connected for a long time with the organization but also proves as an asset for the organization with enhanced efficiency and vigor. In light of the above proof, organizational commitment plays a vital role in reducing employee intention to quit.

workplace ostracism is defined as the inner perceptions of the employees that he or she is being ignored by coworkers or superiors in the organization (Ferris, Brown, et al. 2008). Impact of workplace ostracism call for the detailed investigation to be determined, either ostracism is deliberately or unintentionally (Sommer, Williams, et al. 2001). Being social in nature, group acceptance is the fundamental needs of humans. In the modern era of teamwork and increased performance, mutual communication in the workplace got more importance. Workplace ostracism might cause more pain and harmful and result in the unpleasant situation in the workforce (Sundstrom, McIntyre, et al. 2000). The perceptions of ignorance reduced the social interactions and mutual communications among the workforce in the organization leads to deviating the employees to get their psychological needs at the workplace (Heaphy & Dutton, 2008).

Research shows that workplace ostracism has a negative relationship with job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and turnover intentions, anxiety, and depression have a positive relationship (Ferris, Berry, et al. 2008).

Similarly, another study attempted to examine the phenomenon of ostracism in China. The study was based on self-esteem and participation theories. Employees of the two firms dealing with petroleum and gas were the target population. To remove data bias, three waves were with a gap of four months, used to collect the data from respondents. 443 subordinates working under 120 supervisors were selected as a sample through a random sampling technique. At the final wave, final responses were received from 208 respondents under 96 supervisors utilized from the final analysis. It was found that agreeableness and extraversion were significantly positively related. However, a negative relationship was seen with job performance and self-esteem within the organization (Wu, Wei et al. 2011).

Another study examined workplace ostracism and solicitous behavior in Singapore. The focus of the study was to determine the reaction of the participants who have got ostracized. Data were collected in three steps i.e. scenario, experimental, and field study. The participants of the scenario study were 184 students studying in the universities of Singapore. 140 students were examined in the experimental study segment while in the last segment of the study pairs of the focal participants were contacted with reference to university students of universities in Singapore. It was reported that people with less future orientations have less prosocial behavior with more future orientations with higher prosocial behavior. (Balliet, & Ferris, 2013)

Ostracism is considered to be the most powerful indicator culminating in TI, OC, and job stress. A recent review on ostracism and incivility urge analysts to take a more extensive perspective on abuse develops and to research segregation inside the hypothetical systems of incivility (Ferris, Brown, et al. 2008; Hideg & Ferris, 2017).

Employees commonly experience being ignored in the workplace. Ostracism is considered less harmful than it is in reality; as it affects the well-being, attitude among the workforce and caused turnover (Heaphy and Dutton 2008). It could be concluded from the above literature that WO leads to turnover intentions and finally, the employees leave the job which is very costly for the organization. Assessing the correlation between WO and TI with the mediating process and role of OC would add to fill the gap in the existing literature. The study contains three variables i.e. WO, TI, and OC.

Methodology

Data Collection Procedure

Data was collected through a self-administered, time tested and validated

questionnaire adapted from previous studies. Sample of the study consist of the faculty members of public sector universities in KP. A total of 320 questionnaires were distributed. Responses were received from 224 faculty members, out of which 17 were incomplete and disposed-off.

Research Instruments

Organizational Commitment

To assess organization commitment data was collected through a questionnaire consists of 18 questions adopted from the study of Meyer, Allen et al. (1993). Organizational commitment has three dimensions; each dimension was measured through six questions.

WO

WO scale was used to measure WO. It consists of 10 questions adopted from Ferris, Berry, et al. (2008). For this study, the same scale was adopted to collect the data regarding ostracism in the university teachers of KP.

Turnover Intention

TI among the faculty member of the universities in KP was measured through a 3 point questionnaire adopted from the study of (Camman, Fichman, et al. 1979).

Results

Table 1. Relationship between WO, Dimensions of OC and TI

	WO	AC	CC	NC	TI
Workplace Ostracism	1	-.404**	-.439**	-.405**	.407**

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results show that WO has a significant positive relationship with employees' turnover intention. Furthermore, it is also confirmed that all dimensions of OC have a significant negative correlation with WO.

Table 2. Relationship between WO, Dimensions of OC and TI

	WO	AC	CC	NC	TI
Turnover Intention	.407**	-.281**	-.264**	-.230**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results show that WO has a significant positive correlation with employees' TI. Furthermore, it is also confirmed that all dimensions of OC have a significant negative correlation with TI.

Model 1: Direct Path from WO to Turnover Intention

Structure equation modeling shows the results of a direct path from WO to turnover intention. WO has a significant positive impact on employees' TI. The two factors model (WO and TI) fit the data very well. All values are within the accepting range with chi-square value. The values of GFI, CFI, RMR, and RMSEA are .935, .987, .055 and .050 respectively with chi-square value of 96.5 and degree of freedom, 64.

Model 2: Direct Path from WO to OC

Structure equation modeling shows the result of a direct path from WO to OC. WO hurts OC. The two factors model (WO and OC) fit the data very well. All indices are within the accepting range with chi-square value. The values of GFI, CFI, RMR, and RMSEA are .861, .977, .072 and .045 respectively with chi-square value of 487.9 and degree of freedom, 346.

Based on the results of the study a significant positive relationship was seen between ostracism and turnover intention, it is recommended for the policymakers to focus on ostracism to overcome the problem of turnover. Moreover, the partial mediation of OC reveals that by focusing on it the turnover problems would be minimized.

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